

NEWSLETTER

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OVERALL SURVIVAL – NAVIGATING THE GOLD STANDARD

Welcome to our first issue of 2025! Overall survival (OS) remains the gold standard in oncology clinical trials despite the complexity of its usage and interpretation. Innovative quantitative methodologies, emerging alternative data sources and evolving regulatory landscape are opening new frontiers for navigating the gold standard and finding treatment to cancer.

This issue of newsletter, compiled by the DahShu IDSWG Oncology Working Group, features Dr. Gwise's KOL perspective on biostatisticians' unique role in helping clinicians and patients better understand OS, alongside highlights of the Friends of Cancer Research whitepaper about interim OS data interpretation, a timely contribution to the ongoing discussions about efficient trial design that maintains scientific integrity.

"Estimation of OS using RWD" shares the advances in this area and emphasizes on using high-quality mortality data for reliable results. Crossover handling methodologies, and practical tools like the "trtswitch" R package are also discussed in this issue. Our Biostat Bytes section aims at explaining technical jargons in plain English. In this issue, concepts essential for robust OS estimation such as informative censoring, and counterfactual model are depicted. The Regulatory Corner provides a review of first quarter of 2025 FDA oncology drug approvals, offering context for how OS considerations are influencing regulatory decisions.

This issue also provides an update of the Working Group's key initiatives. A KOL roundtable and panel discussion in oncology dose optimization will take place on May 2 in Waltham, MA. In addition, in collaboration with Therapeutic Innovation and Regulatory Science (TIRS), we are editing a special issue "Recent Advances in Oncology Clinical Trials". We invite experts in the field to submit manuscripts to the special issue. This newsletter also includes highlights of the PharmaDS 2025 conference, an important event discussing AI in drug development. The WG also completed a book chapter about dose optimization and cannot wait to see it in print. We welcome talented and motivated statisticians to join the WG to lead various important initiatives.

We hope you will dive into this newsletter and enjoy your reading – each article represents another step forward in our collective journey to advance clinical cancer research and find treatment to cancer!

Warm regards,

DahShu IDSWG Oncology Working Group

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Edited by:

Haijun Ma, Ph.D.

Philip He, Ph.D.

Laura Fernandes, Ph.D.

Contact us

oncotrialdesign@gmail.com

<https://oncologytrialdesign.org/>

OVERALL SURVIVAL: SOME CURRENT EVENTS

By: THOMAS GWISE #

Overall survival (OS), the time from randomization until death, has been considered the most relevant efficacy endpoint for oncology clinical trials because preventing death is of paramount concern. Currently, closer attention is being paid to the role of OS as an endpoint reflecting safety signals [3, 8]. Although alive vs dead is the starkest of differences, using survival time as an efficacy metric, like cancer drugs, comes with complications. Biostatisticians are uniquely placed to help clinicians and patients better understand complications of OS.

Some challenges we face are due to good news. More and better cancer therapies mean people with cancer can generally look forward to longer lifespans. As life expectancy for cancer patients increases, so does the difficulty in measuring and interpreting OS in clinical trials. Longer survival times tend to increase the probability of patients dropping out of clinical trials with the accompanying possibility of informative censoring. The availability of more treatments that are increasingly effective also means an increased demand for trials that allow crossing to the investigational treatment from the control arm upon treatment failure. Such crossing-over creates a de-facto treatment group: those who received the control therapy followed by the experimental therapy. It also creates interpretation problems. When analyzing such data under an ITT approach, one might expect survival comparisons to be biased toward the null hypothesis. Data from trials where patients receive effective therapies subsequent to the present trial also make it difficult to attribute an OS difference to the therapies in the trial.

Some of these challenges may be managed through good trial design, others ask for innovative analyses, and still others simply demand we do a better job helping our customers and clients understand data and analyses. Thoughtfully utilizing the estimand framework of ICH-E9(R1) [2] can assist in designing trials which result in high quality, interpretable data. While analysis approaches are available for situations like those involving subsequent therapies or competing risks, such approaches often come with assumptions that may not be testable or acceptable to regulators, making a design solution preferable. The use of external control arms, especially those consisting of data from contemporary clinical trials, may be useful in trials where many patients cross to the experimental treatment. Following this path should include addressing the question of whether possible bias from unknown confounders is smaller than the bias associated with cross-over. Methods, such as that in [4] are available to evaluate bias from unknown confounders.

Using a surrogate for OS, such as the time until progression or death (progression free survival or PFS), has been a standard approach to the challenge of excessively long OS trials. I use the word surrogate loosely, understanding that surrogacy according to Prentice's criteria [6] is elusive. While surrogates allow us to avoid lengthy OS trials, they have long been understood to be imperfect [1]. Marino et al [5] cite a set of trials in which surrogacy assumptions were strained, pointing to among other things, inappropriate dosing as a possible culprit. Even when utilizing surrogate endpoints, OS is of interest as a safety endpoint [8]. In trials designed to test efficacy, such OS safety analyses are often ad hoc. Statistical expertise is needed in developing OS safety benchmarks. Friends of Cancer Research recently published a white paper outlining future direction for such activity [3].

I have briefly mentioned a few topics of interest related to OS. I close with some final thoughts. As with most statistical analyses, survival analysis is not intuitive to many outside the statistical community. We biostatisticians can contribute greatly by helping our customers, the clinicians and the patients better understand OS data. Finally, I think biostatisticians can benefit cancer patients immensely by helping them understand their own benefit-risk choices. How do patients and their physicians interpret drug efficacy and safety information when making therapy choices? How would

We biostatisticians can contribute greatly by helping our customers, the clinicians and the patients better understand OS data... understand their own benefit-risk choices.

you integrate information from sections 5, 6 and 14 of a drug label in a way that helps facilitate choice among products? Quality adjusted life years (QALYs) have been used in health economics to weigh benefits and risks in comparing treatments. The QALY has been criticized for not adequately considering perspectives of different groups, most notably the disabled [7]. Patients facing treatment choices would benefit from a methodology similar to QALYs, but designed to integrate and understand drug benefit-risk data in the context of their individual utility parameters. I envision such methodology being facilitated by an app. I am not ignoring the value of groups doing and promoting patient centric comparative effective analyses. I am suggesting we figure out additional ways to unlock information held in data for the benefit of individual patients.

#About the author: Thomas Gwise, PhD is currently an independent consultant who started his consulting business two years ago after 30 years of public service which included leadership positions in the Office of Biostatistics in US FDA.

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Highlights of the Friends of Cancer Research White Paper: Enhancing Study Designs and Interpretation of Interim Overall Survival Data in Oncology Trials

By Philip He[§], Mark Stewart[†]

The white paper, developed by the Friends of Cancer Research in 2024, addresses a pressing challenge in oncology drug development: how to **meaningfully interpret interim overall survival (OS) data** when early endpoints such as progression-free survival (PFS) or objective response rate (ORR) show benefit, but the OS data are immature or conflicting. The paper emphasizes the need for robust trial design, contextualized data interpretation, and structured frameworks to guide regulatory and clinical decision-making.

Early efficacy endpoints enable expedited drug development but often precede mature OS data, which is the gold standard for clinical benefit. Factors such as small numbers of events, limited follow-up, and non-proportional hazards can distort early OS findings. Mistaken conclusions about harm can delay patient access to effective therapies, while ignoring early signs of real harm can pose safety risks.

Several case studies highlight the complexity of interpreting interim OS data: (1) PSMAFore Trial (Prostate Cancer): Although rPFS showed strong benefit, extensive patient crossover confounded OS assessment. (2) monarchE Trial (Early Breast Cancer): Despite early positive IDFS results, initial OS data favored control. With further follow-up, OS hazard ratios trended more favorably, and the FDA expanded the indication. (3) MONALEESA-2 Trial (Metastatic Breast Cancer): Early OS analysis showed HR >1, but later results revealed a statistically significant benefit. This illustrates the danger of relying on immature data with low event counts. (4) Bellini Trial (Multiple Myeloma): Showed PFS benefit but early OS detriment in ITT. One subgroup shows potential OS, but the assessment was limited due to small sample size. (5) PI3K Inhibitors: Demonstrated ORR/PFS benefit but raised serious safety concerns, including OS detriment and toxicities.

Two quantitative frameworks for interpreting interim OS data are discussed: (a) A streamlined quantitative framework offers a simplified, predefined approach for interpreting interim OS data, best suited for trials without patient crossover and with proportional hazards. It focuses on assessing uncertainty around potential harm using pre-specified thresholds—such as minimum event counts, information fraction, and HR confidence interval limits. These thresholds should be tailored to the trial's clinical context, including disease setting, control survival expectations, and unmet medical need. (b) A comprehensive quantitative framework is better suited for complex trials involving non-proportional hazards or patient crossover. It uses a wider range of tools to support deeper analysis when interim OS results are uncertain, incorporating probabilistic assessments and qualitative factors like comorbidities and subsequent therapies. This approach helps ensure that early signs of harm or benefit are not missed due to complex trial dynamics or drug mechanisms.

These two proposed quantitative frameworks can be integrated into a multi-step approach which includes Design, Analysis, and Interpretation Phases. During the design phase, sponsors should pre-specify whether a streamlined or comprehensive quantitative framework will be used. During the analysis phase, perform qualitative assessment (e.g., event counts, adverse events, comorbidities, and subsequent therapies) and quantitative assessment (e.g., HR, confidence intervals, and quantification of uncertainty and potential for harm). During the interpretation phase, synthesize qualitative and quantitative analyses and performing benefit-risk evaluation.

The whitepaper also outlines the emerging **best practices related to clarifying OS as a safety endpoint** when evaluating early endpoint data, trial design considerations, and handling OS data immaturity at interim analysis. The whitepaper is available online at <https://bit.ly/4lyOZnd> and the panel discussion can be viewed at <https://bit.ly/3Yw12aY>.

Reference

Friends of Cancer Research White Paper. Enhancing Study Designs and Interpretation of Interim Overall Survival Data in Oncology Trials, 2024. <https://bit.ly/4lyOZnd>

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[§] Daiichi Sankyo Inc., [†] Friends of Cancer Research

ESTIMATION OF OS USING RWD

By Andrew Belli [§] and Laura Fernandes [§]

Real-world data (RWD) constitute a significant resource for diverse applications throughout the research continuum, encompassing natural history studies, post-marketing investigations, comparative effectiveness analyses employing external controls, and various forms of observational research[1]. RWD is defined as patient data systematically collected within non-clinical trial settings, originating from sources such as electronic health records (EHRs), administrative claims, disease registries, patient-generated health data, and other digital health technologies. There is an increasing utilization of RWD and resultant real-world evidence (RWE) to support regulatory decision-making in new drug applications. This expanded utilization necessitates a greater emphasis on ensuring the quality and completeness of RWD to adequately address research questions pertaining to therapeutic comparative effectiveness. The requirement for RWD validation has been underscored in recent guidance documentation issued by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [2].

Overall survival (OS) is considered a reliable and objective endpoint in oncology research and is thus a preferred endpoint when evaluating the clinical benefit of therapeutic agents. One of the major benefits of complementing clinical trial evidence with RWD is the ability to investigate long-term endpoints such as OS without the requisite trial follow up time, thus saving cost and potentially expediting key therapeutic advances. However, in order to realize the benefits of OS measurement using RWD, the underlying mortality data must be sufficiently complete and accurate to ensure the reliability of results. In randomized controlled trials (RCT), mortality data is well captured due to rigorous study controls and documentation surrounding patient follow up. In the real-world practice setting, mortality data capture is more challenging due to a number of influencing factors including transfer of patient care and incomplete documentation in EHRs [3]. As such, there is a need to establish optimal data standards and collection practices for mortality data in RWD sources.

The National Death Index (NDI) is considered a gold standard for mortality data capture in the United States [4]. However, the NDI is updated annually which may result in delayed data accrual and gaps in contemporary research. Subsequently, researchers utilizing RWD have created composite mortality variables leveraging multiple sources of RWD such as EHR data coupled with commercially available obituary data. It is critical that the validity of these composite real-world endpoints are tested against a gold standard data source, such as the NDI, to ensure reliability for use in comparative effectiveness research.

There are several studies that publish results of the validation of the mortality data [5,6] including a recent publication done at COTA [7]. Such studies demonstrate that using a composite mortality variable that leverages multiple data sources including EHR and obituary data yields high validity when compared against the gold standard NDI. Given existing evidence highlighting the potential challenges of mortality data documentation in the real-world practice setting, the use of a composite mortality variable should be considered a best practice for research.

In selecting a RWD source for estimating OS outcomes, it is important to confirm that the data source captures the mortality information with a high degree of completeness and accuracy. Currently, the established industry practice aggregates mortality data across available data sources to maximize data capture. Metrics from mortality validation studies on the RWD source could be used to evaluate the appropriateness of the data for answering the research question. Having such validation results will provide a benchmark and inform the decision on the expected degree of bias in the estimation of overall survival.

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[§] COTA, Inc.

Short Course Summary

Overall Survival Analysis Methods Correcting for Treatment Switching Effects in Oncology Trials: Theory and SAS/R Code

By Bingxia Wang[§] and Yu-Che Chung[§]

Short Course Title: Overall Survival Analysis Methods Correcting for Treatment Switching Effects in Oncology Trials: Theory and SAS/R Code

Instructors: Jing Xu, Bingxia Wang

Organized by: Takeda Treatment Switching Working Group

Contributors: Jing Xu, Bingxia Wang, Guohui Liu, Camden Bay, Cong Li, Donghui Yang (Takeda Pharmaceuticals)

Event: JSM 2024 and RISW 2024 (August & September 2024); invited by the America Statistical Association as a [travelling course in 2025](#).

In August and September 2024, the Takeda Treatment Switching Working Group hosted a short course at the JSM 2024 and RISW 2024 conferences. This course focused on four complex statistical methods used to recover causal effects of randomized active interventions on overall survival (OS) in oncology clinical trials that allow for treatment switching, including Marginal Structural Model (MSM), Two-Stage Estimation (TSE), Inverse Probability of Censoring Weighting (IPCW), and Rank Preserving Structure Failure Time Model (RPSFTM).

In many late-phase oncology randomized controlled trials (RCTs), patients in the control arm may be allowed to switch to an active treatment (1-way crossover), or both arms may allow for alternative treatments after disease progression (2-way treatment switching). These switches complicate the estimation of causal treatment effects on OS, as the observed data no longer directly reflect the randomized treatment allocation. While intent-to-treat (ITT) analysis captures the trial outcome under the treatment policy, it cannot reliably infer the causal effect of the active intervention on OS, which is crucial for regulatory evaluations and payer decisions.

Over the last decade, four advanced statistical methods—MSM, TSE, IPCW, and RPSFTM—have been increasingly adapted to recover causal treatment effects in the presence of treatment switching. The short course offered a comprehensive and in-depth review of these approaches, covering their theoretical foundations, key assumptions, strengths and limitations, practical applications in real-world studies, and implementation using both SAS and R programming languages.

- **Methodology:** A summary table highlighting the key assumptions and limitations of each method is provided in Table 1.
- **Practical Implementation:** Through case studies, participants learned how to construct longitudinal datasets in SAS for treatment switching settings and implement SAS/R code for each method.
- **Practice recommendation**
 - No method is uniformly the “best” approach
 - Up front planning (data collection to satisfy the assumptions for the approaches to be used)
 - Pre-specify analysis details in the SAP, including a complete list of confounding covariates and variable selection method, etc.
 - Early engagement with regulatory agencies
 - More than one method (better if belonging to different classes) needs to be used to demonstrate the robustness of the causal OS treatment benefit

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[§] Takeda Pharmaceuticals

- **Regulatory and Design Considerations:** The course emphasized the importance of selecting appropriate statistical methods during trial design and pre-specifying analysis strategies in the statistical analysis plan, recognizing that no single method is universally applicable. Additionally, regulatory and HTA agencies hold differing perspectives on treatment switching. In general, regulatory agencies prefer evaluating efficacy based on the ITT principle without adjustment and consider adjustment methods as supportive analyses. In contrast, HTA agencies focus on real-world effectiveness and cost effectiveness, favoring adjusted OS estimates to better capture long-term outcomes.
- **Hands-On Training:** Participants gained practical experience with SAS macros to generate weighted log-rank tests and adjusted survival curves for different treatment switching scenarios.

At the conclusion of the course, participants were equipped to apply these statistical methods in real-world RCT settings, enhancing their ability to make informed, causally valid inferences about the effects of active treatments on OS.

Table 1. Summary of Methods addressing treatment switching

Method	Key Assumptions	Strength	Limitation
RPSFTM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common treatment effect (May not be true for oncology RCT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs no covariate information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased SE by re-censoring and bootstrap • Shortened placebo arm in adjusted KM plot
TSE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No unmeasured confounding (manageable for RCT via pre-specification in SAP). • OS data follows parametric distribution. • No gap time b/t progression and crossover. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No common treatment effect assumption • Efficient • SE may be estimated via data driven robust variance • Data may be summarized via adjusted Stat. and KM curve like ITT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not meet key assumption perfectly
IPCW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No unmeasured confounding (Manageable for RCT via pre-specification in SAP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No common treatment effect assumption • SE may be estimated via data driven robust variance • Data may be summarized via adjusted Stat. and KM curve like ITT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider 95% CIs due to information loss from censoring the post-crossover data • Need to meet positivity and consistency assumption • May fail if too many (or too few) patients switched • May not meet key assumption perfectly
MSM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No unmeasured confounding (Manageable for RCT via pre-specification in SAP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No common treatment effect assumption • SE may be estimated via data driven robust variance • Uses more data than IPCW • Data may be summarized via adjusted Stat. and KM curve like ITT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to meet positivity and consistency assumption • May fail if too many (or too few) patients switched • May not meet key assumption perfectly

References: [Continued on page 10]

trtswitch package in RBy Kaifeng Lu[§]

The *Treatment Switch* Workstream of the ASA BIOP Statistical Methods in Oncology Scientific Working Group has identified the lack of a comprehensive and flexible software package for adjusting survival time estimates in the presence of treatment switching as a critical unmet need. Three primary adjustment methods for handling treatment switching are outlined in NICE TSD 16 and TSD 24: rank preserving structural failure time model (RPSFTM), iterative parameter estimation (IPE), inverse probability of censoring weights (IPCW), and two-stage estimation (TSE).

The *rpsftm* package in R implements the RPSFTM approach and includes a `treat_modifier` parameter, which allows for relaxation of the common treatment effect assumption. However, the package does not provide an adjusted hazard ratio estimate from a Cox model when the time ratio parameter (Ψ) is derived from the log-rank test, a commonly used practice.

The *ipcwswitch* package in R implements the IPCW approach, using a Cox model with time-dependent covariates to estimate each subject's probability of switching over time. However, the package has two key limitations:

1. The `cens.ipw` function does not censor events at the time of treatment switching if the patient dies after switching.
2. The `ipcw` function calculates inverse probability of censoring weights using survival probabilities from the start rather than the end of the time interval for time-dependent covariates.

To address these limitations, the *trtswitch* package in R was developed, providing a unified framework that supports all three primary adjustment methods outlined in NICE TSD 16 and TSD 24. The package includes the following functions: `rpsftm`, `ipe`, `ipcw`, `tsesimp` (simple two-stage estimation), and `tsegest` (two-stage estimation with g-estimation).

Key features of the *trtswitch* package:

- For RPSFTM, IPE, and TSE, a censor parameter enables analysis with or without recensoring.
- For IPCW, the switching model can be implemented using either pooled logistic regression or proportional hazards regression with time-dependent covariates, and weights can be truncated and stabilized.
- All adjustment methods support the use of stratification factors and the inclusion of baseline covariates.
- All adjustment methods allow bootstrap resampling.
- Outputs from all adjustment methods are designed to align with the reporting guidelines outlined in NICE TSD 24.
- The core computational functions are implemented in C++, enabling high-speed performance.

The Treatment Switching Code Standardization sub-team is currently validating the functionalities of the *trtswitch* package and developing R Markdown templates to automate the generation of reports that comply with NICE TSD 24 reporting guidelines.

Additionally, the sub-team is working on the adjustment method using marginal structural models (MSMs). A website is currently being developed to host the programs and case studies, as well as to gather comments and feedback on the standardized code.

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[§] Takeda Pharmaceuticals

Analysis of Cross-over
Tools and ExamplesBy Mei Huang¹ and Haijun Ma²

Implementation of some of the statistical methods to handle crossover can be challenging. Several R packages and SAS macros are available to facilitate this process. Published case studies and regulatory review documents could also provide useful insights. While not exhaustive, a list of tools and case studies that may serve as a helpful resource is compiled as follows.

R Package	Methods	Reference
<i>rpsftm</i>	RPSFTM	Allison A, White IR, Bond S. <i>rpsftm</i> : An R Package for Rank Preserving Structural Failure Time Models. R J. 2017 Dec 4;9(2):342-353. PMID: 29564164; PMCID: PMC5858764.; Available on CRAN
<i>rpsftmPlus</i>	RPSFTM	Bennett I (2022). <i>rpsftmPlus</i> : Extensions To Rpsftm Package. R package version 1.0.0.; Available on Github
<i>trtswitch</i>	RPSFTM, IPE, IPCW, and TSE	Kaifeng Lu <i>trtswitch</i> .pdf Available on CRAN
<i>ipcwswitch</i>	IPCW	Graffé N, Latouche A, Le Tourneau C, Chevret S. <i>ipcwswitch</i> : An R package for inverse probability of censoring weighting with an application to switches in clinical trials. <i>Comput Biol Med.</i> 2019 Aug;111:103339. doi: 10.1016/j.combiomed.2019.103339. Epub 2019 Jun 24. PMID: 31442762.; Available on CRAN

SAS program/macro	Methods	Source
A combination of DATA step programming and iterative %find_U macro processing in order to obtain the estimate for Ψ .	RPSFTM	Danner BJ, Sarkar I. 2018. "Implementing the Rank-Preserving Structural Failure Time Model in SAS and R". PharmaSUG 2018 Conference Proceedings.
%rpsftm %ipcw	RPSFTM IPCW	Mosier B. 2023. "Survival Methods for Crossover in Oncology Trials". PharmaSUG proceedings, Paper AP-191.
Macros to generate counting process style data for IPCW analysis modified IPCW macro based on Mosier's version	IPCW	Huang M., Harite S., Zhang L., Ma H. 2025. "Implementation of the Inverse Probability of Censoring Weighting (IPCW) Model in Oncology Trials". PharmaSUG proceedings, Paper ST-343. (Accepted)

Case studies:

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Date	Generic Name/Link	Indication
1/16/2025	<u>acalabrutinib with bendamustine and rituximab</u>	adults with previously untreated mantle cell lymphoma who are ineligible for autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation
1/16/2025	<u>sotorasib with panitumumab</u>	adult patients with KRAS G12C-mutated metastatic colorectal cancer
1/17/2025	<u>datopotamab deruxtecan-dlnk</u>	adult patients with unresectable or metastatic, hormone receptor-positive, human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-negative breast cancer
1/21/2025	<u>treosulfan</u>	acute myeloid leukemia or myelodysplastic syndrome
1/27/2025	<u>fam-trastuzumab deruxtecan-nxki</u>	unresectable or metastatic hormone receptor-positive, HER2-low or HER2-ultralow breast cancer
2/11/2025	<u>mirdametinib</u>	adult and pediatric patients 2 years of age and older with neurofibromatosis type 1 who have symptomatic plexiform neurofibromas not amenable to complete resection
2/11/2025	<u>brentuximab vedotin</u>	adult patients with relapsed or refractory large B-cell lymphoma
2/14/2025	<u>vimseltinib</u>	adult patients with symptomatic tenosynovial giant cell tumor
3/19/2025	<u>pembrolizumab</u>	adults with locally advanced unresectable or metastatic HER2-positive gastric or gastroesophageal junction adenocarcinoma whose tumors express PD-L1
3/26/2025	<u>cabozantinib</u>	adult and pediatric patients 12 years of age and older with previously treated, unresectable, locally advanced or metastatic, well-differentiated pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors and well-differentiated extra-pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors
3/28/2025	<u>LUTETIUM LU-177 VIPIVOTIDE TETRAXETAN</u>	adults with prostate-specific membrane antigen-positive metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer
3/28/2025	<u>durvalumab with gemcitabine and cisplatin</u>	adults with muscle invasive bladder cancer
4/8/2025	<u>nivolumab with ipilimumab</u>	unresectable or metastatic microsatellite instability-high or mismatch repair deficient colorectal cancer
4/11/2025	<u>nivolumab with ipilimumab</u>	unresectable or metastatic hepatocellular carcinoma
4/23/2025	<u>penpulimab-kcqx</u>	recurrent or metastatic non-keratinizing nasopharyngeal carcinoma;

SOME STATISTICAL CONCEPTS FOR OS ESTIMATION

BY SHIYU ZHANG ²

Crossover

Crossover means switching patients from one treatment to another at a certain point during the trial. A patient who initially receives drug A might later be switched ("crossed over") to receive drug B. In oncology clinical trials, **crossover** usually refers to the practice of allowing patients in the control arm (such as those receiving placebo or standard of care) to switch to the investigational treatment, typically after disease progression. While this approach is often driven by ethical considerations, especially when early evidence suggests treatment benefit, it introduces **important statistical challenges** when interpreting endpoints like **overall survival (OS)** [1]. Because crossover occurs after disease progression, progression-free survival (PFS) is typically unaffected and can serve as a clean measure of treatment efficacy. However, OS may be biased, as patients in both arms may ultimately receive the investigational drug. This treatment "contamination" can dilute the observed survival benefit in intention-to-treat (ITT) analyses, leading to an underestimation of the true effect.

Counterfactual model

The counterfactual model is a key concept in causal inference. It asks: What would have happened to a patient if they had received a different treatment than the one they actually got? Each individual has two potential outcomes: one if they receive the treatment, and one if they do not. However, in practice, we only observe one of these outcomes per person—the one under the treatment they actually received. The causal effect is defined as the difference between these two potential outcomes. Since we can never observe both outcomes for the same person, we estimate average causal effects across groups, such as the average treatment effect (ATE), which compares the average difference in outcomes between individuals who receive a treatment and those who do not, across the entire population. In randomized trials, randomization helps ensure comparability between groups. In observational studies, methods like propensity score matching are used to adjust for confounding and approximate the missing counterfactual outcomes [5].

Figure 1: Illustration of the design and analysis of a randomized crossover trial [2]

Biostat Bytes

Some Statistical Concepts for OS Estimation

By Shiyu Zhang[†]

Informative censoring

Informative censoring arises when the likelihood of a patient being censored is related to their risk of the event. In randomized clinical trials with PFS as the primary endpoint, this often occurs when dropout rates differ between arms, such as when patients on the experimental treatment discontinue early due to toxicity or poor tolerability [3]. Because these patients often have different risk profiles than those who remain on study, the censoring is considered informative, violating the assumption of non-informative censoring used in standard Kaplan-Meier (KM) analysis.

This violation can introduce significant bias into time-to-event endpoint estimates, such as PFS estimates. As illustrated in Figure 2 from [4], censoring high-risk patients leads to an overestimation of PFS, while censoring low-risk patients leads to an underestimation of PFS.

Tipping point

Tipping point analysis is a sensitivity analysis method used to assess how missing data might affect the conclusions of a clinical trial. In oncology and other therapeutic areas, missing outcomes are common due to patient dropout, loss to follow-up, or other disruptions. When the reason for missing data may relate to patient outcomes, traditional analyses assuming “missing at random” may not be reliable.

Tipping point analysis addresses this by systematically assigning a range of plausible values to the missing data, starting from the most favorable assumption (e.g., all missing patients responded) to the least favorable (e.g., none responded). The “tipping point” is the scenario at which the study’s conclusion changes, for instance, when a statistically significant treatment effect becomes non-significant.

This approach is especially useful when no clear assumption about the missingness mechanism can be justified. By exploring a spectrum of outcomes, tipping point analysis reveals how robust or fragile the trial’s conclusions are to uncertainty caused by missing data. It’s a transparent and intuitive way to support decision-making, even in the face of incomplete evidence.

Figure 2 The anticipated direction of the bias in the 12-month and median PFS estimates is shown when patients who come off study are at a higher risk for progression (A, B) or a lower risk for progression (C, D).

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[†] Merck

PharmaDS 2025 Conference

By Rebecca Jones-Taha¹ and Philip He²

PharmaDS 2025 opened April 7 in Edison, NJ, under the banner “Re-imagining the Future of Pharma: AI-Powered Value Creation,” with Co-Chairs Dr. Rebecca D. Jones-Taha (waterworksAI) and Dr. Philip He (Daiichi Sankyo) welcoming over 100 organizations from around the country. The conference kicked-off to highly reviewed short courses offered by distinguished industry and academic leaders, which included (1) Tutorial on Deep Learning and GenAI (Prof. Shen, UMN and Dr. Fu, Amgen); (2) GenAI content in pharmaceutical development: Exploring methods and techniques (Dr. Taha et al, waterworksai); (3) Unleashing the Power of Machine Learning and Deep Learning to Accelerate Clinical Development (Dr. Wang et al, Abbvie); and (4) Biomedical Large Language Models – Development and Application (Prof. Xu, Yale U; Prof. Peng, Cornell U).

Dr. Michael R. Kosorok (UNC-Chapel Hill) delivered a compelling keynote on AI-driven precision health—highlighting work on gestational age prediction using blind ultrasound sweeps and reinforcement-learning treatment algorithms. A high-impact panel moderated by Dr. He brought together experts from BeOne Medicines and academia, debating the evolution of large language models, practical implementation challenges, and ownership of AI functions. Technical deep dives included sessions on dynamic treatment regimes, hybrid control-arm methodologies, and a visionary “Protocol Builder” platform that uses RAG and templating to automate critical regulatory documents—while embedding patient feedback loops to enhance equity and access.

Day 2 of the main conference showcased end-to-end AI innovations in clinical and commercial functions. Seagle Liu (Veracyte), Xiaoyan Wang (Tulane University), and Clara Wang (AbbVie) demonstrated large-scale real-world data linkage and AI-powered evidence synthesis for next-generation diagnostics. Mid-morning, teams highlighted how generative AI can compress systematic literature reviews from months to hours without sacrificing accuracy. In a standout session, Juan Araque (Johnson & Johnson) unpacked causal AI frameworks for pharma manufacturing—illustrating structural causal models, root-cause analysis, and decision-optimization pipelines that drive both quality and efficiency. The conference culminated in networking forums—spurring cross-disciplinary discussion on AI adoption roadmaps and collaboration opportunities.

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waterworksAI and Daiichi Sankyo

WORKING GROUP HIGHLIGHTS

- Upcoming KOL roundtable and panel discussion scheduled on May 2, 2025 in Waltham, MA, about oncology dose optimization.
- Leading the special issue "Recent Advances in Oncology Clinical Trials" in the journal of Therapeutics Innovation and Regulatory Science.
- Completed a book chapter on oncology dose optimization.
- Submitted manuscripts in the practice of master protocol studies and PFS/OS endpoints in oncology.
- RISW 2025 Session in RWD was accepted.
- Multiple presentations were accepted by JSM 2025 and RISW 2025.
- A manuscript on platform trials has been accepted for publication in Therapeutic Innovation & Regulatory Science

[Link to TIRS](#)

Upcoming Conferences

[The 10th Workshop on Biostatistics and Bioinformatics](#)

May 09 - May 11, Atlanta, Georgia

Event Type: Workshops & Seminars

[The 16th annual UMBC Probability and Statistics Conference](#)

May 9-10, University of Maryland Bltimore County.

[The 8th Stat4Onc AnnualSymposium](#),

May 16-17, 2025, Stanford University, CA

Where Oncology and Statistics meet, communicate, and synergize!

[The fourth Lifetime Data Science \(LiDS\) Conference](#)

May 28-30, 2025, Brooklyn, New York, USA

Lifetime Data Science and the World

[2025 WJAR/IMS Annual Meeting](#)

June 15 - June 18, 2025, WHISTLER, BC, CANADA

[2025 ICSA Applied Statistics Symposium](#)

June 15 – June 18, 2025, Storrs, Connecticut, USA,

Insights into Complexity: Empowering Policy through Statistical Learning and Data Analytics

[The 14th International Conference on Bayesian](#)

[Nonparametrics \(BNP14\)](#) and the first ever Bayesian

[Biostatistics and Pharmaceutical Conference \(BBP 2025\)](#), UCLA, Los Angeles, from June 23-27, 2025.

A workshop on the [25th Anniversary of the Dependent Dirichlet Process](#) and a [workshop on Bayesian Predictive Inference](#) for Sunday, June 22nd, 2025.

[39th International Workshop on Statistical Modelling](#)

Sunday 13th July to Friday 18th July 2025, the Strand Hotel, Limerick City, Ireland

workshop dedicated to statistical modelling

[R/Pharma 2025 virtual conference](#), Nov 3-7, 2025

[The 2025 Women in Statistics and Data Science conference](#)

Nov 12-14, Cincinnati, Ohio

Thank you for reading!

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